

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE

San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office
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Sacramento, California 95814

In reply refer to:
2024-0111150-S7-001

August 27, 2024

Gregory Brown
Senior Regulatory Project Manager
Regulatory Division
San Francisco District
U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
450 Golden Gate Avenue, 4th Floor
San Francisco, CA 94102

Subject: Formal and Informal Consultation for the 505 E. Bayshore Road Remedial Sediment and Soil Cleanup Project, City of Redwood City, San Mateo County, California (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers File Number: SPN-2020-00467)

Dear Mr. Brown:

This letter is in response to the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers' (Corps) June 25, 2024, letter requesting informal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) on the 505 E. Bayshore Road Remedial Sediment and Soil Cleanup Project (proposed project) in the City of Redwood City, San Mateo County, California. The Corps determined that the project may affect and is not likely to adversely affect the endangered California Ridgway's rail (*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*) and the endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*). This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR 402).

In reviewing this project, the Service has relied upon: (1) the Corps' June 25, 2024, letter requesting consultation; (2) the updated biological assessment dated July 18, 2024; and (3) other information available to the Service.

The Service concurs that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the California Ridgway's rail. Suitable habitat is sparse and nesting habitat does not occur in the proposed project area. According to the biological assessment suitable habitat does occur approximately 1,400 linear feet from the proposed project area. California Ridgway's rails occur within Bair Island but surveys near the proposed project area have not resulted in detections. Based on these reasons, it is reasonable to assume California Ridgway's are unlikely to occur in or immediately adjacent to the proposed project area.

However, the Service does not concur with the Corps' determination that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the salt marsh harvest mouse. Suitable habitat does occur within the proposed project area and the biological assessment describes the potential for adverse effects to occur if salt marsh harvest mice are present. Additionally, the conclusion in the biological assessment for the salt marsh harvest mouse confuses an Action Agency's not likely to adversely affect determination with the Service's jeopardy analysis in the conclusion of a biological opinion. Therefore, the remainder of this document is the Service's biological opinion on the effects of the proposed project salt marsh harvest mouse.

Consultation History

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| June 25, 2024 | The Service received the Corps' consultation request with a biological assessment dated June 2024. |
| July 19, 2024 | The Service received the Corps' email transmitting the updated biological assessment dated July 18, 2024. |

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The proposed project is located within a muted tidal ditch at 505 E. Bayshore Road in Redwood City south of Inner Bair Island. The muted tidal ditch abuts Alan Steel & Supply Company along the southern boundary and a pedestrian trail along the northern boundary and is hydrologically connected by a 16-inch diameter corrugated culvert to a full tidal slough channel adjacent to the Inner Bair Island trail.

The proposed project involves removing soil and sediment containing polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and removing and replacing approximately 2,250 tons of soil and sediment containing PCBs at and near 505 East Bayshore Road in Redwood City. The proposed elements below are described as the sequence of work as presented in the biological assessment.

1. During a low tide, the muted tidal ditch will be allowed to fully drain to ensure no fish remain within the ditch. Once drained the culvert will be plugged to prevent tidal water and fish from entering the drainage ditch and to prevent sediment from entering Smith Slough.
2. Mobilization of the staging area, and work, will occur on the commercial property at 505 E. Bayshore Road. The fence separating the commercial property from the drainage ditch will be removed and replaced with a temporary fence, the 4-inch polyvinyl chloride (PVC) pipe valve will be closed, the pipe entering the work area will be cut and removed. Geomembrane, and straw waddles will be placed in the location where excavated material will be temporarily placed prior to hauling the material offsite or where soil will be direct loaded into trucks for offsite upland disposal.
3. Under the guidance of the biologist, all vegetation along the southern boundary of the ditch in areas that will be excavated will be removed using hand tools and disposed at an upland location. Under the guidance of the biologist and at least twenty-four hours prior

to the start of excavation, the contractor will remove all vegetation throughout the entire work zone along the southern boundary using hand tools. Once the vegetation has been removed and 24 hours has passed, a wildlife barrier will be installed across the channel along the eastern boundary to prevent animals from entering the work zone.

4. Using a long arm excavator and/or clamshell bucket, working from the top of the ditch on the commercial property side (south side), soil will be excavated and either staged on the commercial property to allow stockpiles sufficient time to passively air dry or by adding a water-binding additive (such as cement) to remove the free water, or put directly into trucks for off-site disposal.
5. Once removal of soil is complete, geotextile fabric will be placed along the bottom of the channel and a three-dimensional geotextile cellular structure composed of high-density polyethylene or polypropylene, also referred to as geocells, will be installed at the base of the excavated area up along the side slope of the southern boundary of the ditch. The geotextile materials will provide a demarcation layer and stability of the backfill material. Clean cover will then be placed over the geotextile materials to backfill the excavated areas, bringing them up to pre-project grades. Once the areas are brought up to grade an approximately 9-inch wide low flow channel will be graded to facilitate flows to and from the culvert. Following work, the areas proposed for re-vegetation will be planted with native vegetation to augment the natural plant recruitment that will occur once the ditch is opened back up to tidal flows.

Staging for construction equipment, stock piling material, and loading trucks will occur on the Alan Steel & Supply Company property.

Construction is expected be conducted during the dry season to avoid the winter rainy season. If construction extends into the rainy season, appropriate stormwater best management practices will be implemented in accordance with the National Pollution Discharge Elimination System (NPDES) General Permit for Storm Water Discharges Associated with Construction and Land Disturbance Activities Order No.: 2022-0057-DWQ, NPDES No. CAS000002.

Conservation Measures

1. The biological monitor(s) will provide an endangered species training program to all personnel involved in project construction to include all project managers, inspectors, equipment operators, and construction workers. At a minimum, the employee education program will consist of a brief presentation by persons knowledgeable about salt marsh harvest mouse biology and legislative protection to explain concerns to contractors, their employees, and agency personnel involved with implementation of the proposed project. The program will include the following: a description of the species and their habitat needs, any reports of occurrences in the Action Area; an explanation of the status of the salt marsh harvest mouse and their protection under the Act; and a list of measures being taken to reduce impacts to these species during the work, and the biologist's contact information. Fact sheets containing this information will be distributed to all involved in the training.
2. At least 24 hours prior to commencement of construction, pickleweed and other vegetation will be removed from the Remediation Area using hand tools. Prior to removal

of vegetation, a qualified (a biologist with at least two years of experience monitoring construction sites for salt marsh harvest mice) biological monitor will walk the work zone to ensure no salt marsh harvest mice or nests exist.

3. Once vegetation removal is complete and a minimum of 24 hours has passed, temporary wildlife exclusion fencing will be placed across the drainage ditch along the eastern boundary of the Remediation Area to prevent salt marsh harvest mice from moving into the construction area. The fence should be made of a material that does not allow salt marsh harvest mice to pass through (e.g., a standard silt fence) and the bottom should be buried to a depth of four to six inches so that mice cannot crawl under the fence. All support for the exclusion fencing should be facing toward the inside of the proposed project area.
4. If a mouse species is observed at any time during construction, work will not be initiated or will be stopped immediately until the mouse leaves the vicinity of the work area on its own volition. If the mouse does not leave the work area, work will not be reinitiated until the Service is contacted and has made a decision on how to proceed with work activities. The biological monitor(s) will direct the contractor on how to proceed accordingly. The biological monitor(s) or any other persons at the site will not pursue, capture, handle or harass any rail or mouse observed.
5. All trash (e.g., food scraps, cans, bottles, containers, wrappers, cigarette butts, and other discarded items) will be placed in closed containers and properly disposed of offsite on a daily basis.
6. Erosion control devices, such as straw waddles, will be free of nylon mesh that could entrap animals.
7. Hazardous materials used during the work period (e.g., fuels, lubricants, solvents, etc.) will be controlled, cleaned up, and properly disposed of outside the tidal marsh areas. Refueling areas for any equipment will be located at upland sites outside of wetlands.
8. After construction, a final clean-up will include removal of the wildlife barrier and all refuse generated by the work.
9. If requested, before, during, or upon completion of construction, the construction contractor will allow access by Service personnel to the work areas to inspect effects, if any, of the actions on the salt marsh harvest mouse.

Action Area

The Action Area is defined in 50 CFR § 402.02, as “all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action”. For the purposes of the effects assessment, the approximately 3.82-acre Action Area includes the Remediation Area where all work will be occurring, the abutting Alan Steel & Supply Company yard where work and staging will occur, and the entire drainage ditch that will be dewatered (Figure 1, Figure 3 in the biological assessment).

Figure 1. Action Area

Analytical Framework for the Jeopardy Determination

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that Federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. “Jeopardize the continued existence of” means to engage in an action that reasonably would be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed Federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the range wide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the current range wide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the current condition of the species in the Action Area without the consequences to the listed species caused by the proposed action, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the Action Area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which includes all effects that are caused by the proposed Federal action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action but that are not part of the action; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-Federal activities in the Action Area on the species. The *Effects of the Action* and *Cumulative Effects* are added to the *Environmental Baseline* and in

light of the status of the species, the Service formulates its opinion as to whether the proposed action is likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species.

Status of the Species

There are two subspecies of the salt marsh harvest mouse: the northern subspecies (*R. r. halicoetes*) and the southern subspecies (*R. r. raviventris*) both of which are listed as endangered. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. Threats evaluated during the drafting of the recovery plan and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since its publication, with loss of habitat being the most significant effect. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the salt marsh harvest mouse 5-year review at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/tess/species_nonpublish/3643.pdf (Service 2021). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review.

Environmental Baseline

Environmental Baseline refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the Action Area, without the consequences to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The *Environmental Baseline* includes the past and present impacts of all Federal, State, or private actions and other human activities in the Action Area, the anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal projects in the Action Area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the *Environmental Baseline*.

The Action Area is situated along a San Francisco Bay Trail (Bay Trail) adjacent to Inner Bair Island. It is situated on a muted tidal drainage ditch, and historic baylands. Uplands include a levee that provides flood protection, Bay Trail, commercial properties, and a culvert. The muted tidal drainage ditch receives stormwater from the adjacent commercial business and muted tidal flows through a 36-inch corrugated culvert from a tidal slough which is connected to Smith Slough.

There are two vegetated communities within the Remediation Area: estuarine intertidal emergent wetland and estuarine intertidal unconsolidated bottom using the Cowardin classification system and urban habitat as identified by according to the California Wildlife Habitat Relationship system. Urban habitat within the Remediation Area and staging areas is located in uplands on the Pacific Gas and Electric Company levee trail and adjacent inboard side of the levee. The majority of the upland urban habitat area are developed with hardscape surfaces with the exception of a strip along the pedestrian trail which is dominated by ripgut brome (*Bromus diandrus*), and saltgrass (*Distichlis spicata*).

The majority of remediation would occur within the estuarine intertidal unconsolidated bottom wetland habitat. Along the southern boundary remediation work will encroach into approximately 0.09-acre of sparsely vegetated wetlands classified as estuarine intertidal emergent wetlands. These wetlands occur along a 2-foot-wide strip sparsely vegetated with

pickleweed (*Salicornia pacifica*), alkali heath (*Frankenia grandifolia*), and saltgrass (*Distichlis spicata*). The estuarine intertidal emergent wetland along the full tidal slough and along the northern slope of the muted tidal drainage ditch provides suitable foraging and nesting habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse.

The biological assessment states the nearest known reported occurrence of salt marsh harvest mouse to the Action Area is located approximately 1,300 linear feet northeast of the Action Area in a tidal marsh across from Seaport Centre in Redwood City along Smith Slough. Salt marsh harvest mice are also known to occur within the Service's Don Edwards San Francisco Bay National Wildlife Refuge Inner Bair Island. There have been no documented sightings of the species in the Action Area but the level of effort to survey or document sightings is not known. The salt marsh habitat outboard of the levee trail within Smith Slough and the habitat on the northern boundary of the drainage ditch are considered suitable habitat for salt marsh harvest mouse. Therefore, based on known occurrences near the Action Area and presence of suitable habitat, it is reasonable to assume that salt marsh harvest mice may occur within the salt marsh habitats in the Action Area.

Effects of the Action

Effects of the Action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it would not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. *Effects of the Action* may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action.

The proposed project includes temporarily dewatering the drainage ditch by plugging the culvert during low tide, removal of vegetation on the south side of the drainage ditch, and installation of a wildlife barrier along the eastern boundary to prevent animals from entering the work zone. The use of construction equipment within the marsh and the dewatering of a portion of the marsh have the potential to result in adverse effects to salt marsh harvest mice and their habitat.

Individuals may be disturbed by the operation of equipment and the activities of work crews conducting construction activities at that site. Such disturbance could cause individuals to disperse, could result in harm or even mortality, or could cause individuals to remain more susceptible to predation during high tide events. Habitat removal could result in nest destruction or abandonment. These adverse effects will be partially minimized by conducting preconstruction surveys for salt marsh harvest mice, removing all marsh vegetation within the Remediation Area using hand tools, and then installing wildlife barrier fencing to prevent salt marsh harvest mice from entering the work area.

The Service anticipates removal of PCBs and soil remediation would result in long-term beneficial improvement to the overall habitat within the Action Area and in areas tidally connected to the Action Area.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local, or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area considered in this biological opinion. Future

Federal actions that are unrelated to the proposed project are not considered in this section; they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During this consultation, the Service did not identify any future non-Federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area of the proposed project.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current *Status of the Species*, the *Environmental Baseline*, the *Effects of the Action*, and the *Cumulative Effects*, it is the Service's biological opinion that 505 E. Bayshore Road Remedial Sediment and Soil Cleanup Project is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the salt marsh harvest mouse. This conclusion is primarily based on: (1) the small size and scope of the proposed project; (2) implementation of the *Conservation Measures* to minimize the adverse effects on individual salt marsh harvest mice and its habitat during the construction; and (3) the removal of contaminated sediment would offset temporary habitat impacts, as the overall quality of the habitat would be improved and result long-term habitat benefits.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harass is defined by Service regulations at 50 CFR 17.3 as an intentional or negligent act or omission which creates the likelihood of injury to wildlife by annoying it to such an extent as to significantly disrupt normal behavior patterns which include, but are not limited to, breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Harm is defined by the same regulations as an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Harm is further defined to include significant habitat modification or degradation that results in death or injury to listed species by significantly impairing essential behavior patterns, including breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Incidental take is defined as take that is incidental to, and not the purpose of, the carrying out of an otherwise lawful activity. Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking that is incidental to and not intended as part of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act provided that such taking is in compliance with the terms and conditions of this Incidental Take Statement.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the Corps so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicant, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Corps has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Corps (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions or (2) fails to require the applicant to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the Corps must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR §402.14(i)(4)].

Amount or Extent of Take

The Service anticipates incidental take of salt marsh harvest mice will be difficult to detect or quantify because of their inherently elusive behavior, propensity to move rapidly through vegetation, and their cryptic occupancy in tidal marsh habitats resulting in low detectability. Due to the difficulty in quantifying the number of salt marsh harvest mice that will be taken as a result of the proposed project, the number of acres of affected habitat becomes a surrogate for the species that will be taken. The Service anticipates that all salt marsh harvest mice within the 3.82-acre Action Area may be subject to incidental take in the form of harm, injury, and mortality as described in this biological opinion. Upon implementation of the following reasonable and prudent measures, incidental take of salt marsh harvest mice associated with the proposed project will become exempt from the prohibitions described in section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this opinion.

Effect of the Take

The Service determines that the level of take is not likely to result in jeopardy to the salt marsh harvest mouse.

Reasonable and Prudent Measure

The following reasonable and prudent measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize the effects of the proposed project to the salt marsh harvest mouse:

1. Adverse effects to salt marsh harvest mice shall be minimized to the full extent possible.

Term and Condition

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Corps, shall ensure that its contractors comply with the following term and condition, which implement its respective reasonable and prudent measure described above. This term and condition is non-discretionary.

1. Term and Condition 1 implements Reasonable and Prudent Measure 1:

- a. The Corps and/or applicant shall implement the *Conservation Measures* as described in the *Description of the Proposed Action* and comply with this biological opinion.
- b. At least 15 days prior to the onset of any construction-related activities, the Corps or the applicant shall submit to the Service, for approval, the name(s) and credentials of biologist(s) it requests to conduct activities specified for this project. Information included in a request for authorization must include, at a minimum: (1) relevant education; (2) relevant training on species identification, survey techniques, handling individuals of different age classes, and handling of different life stages by a permitted biologist or recognized species expert authorized for such activities by the Service; (3) a summary of field experience conducting requested activities (to include project/research information and actual experience with the species); (4) a summary of biological opinions and/or informal consultations under which they were authorized to work with the listed species and at what level (such as construction monitoring versus handling), this should also include the names

and qualifications of persons under which the work was supervised as well as the amount of work experience on the actual project including detail on whether the species was encountered or not; and (5) a list of Federal Recovery Permits [10(a)1(A)] if any, held or under which individuals are authorized to work with the species (to include permit number, authorized activities, and name of permit holder). No project activities shall begin until the Applicant and/or the Corps has received written Service approval for biologists to conduct specified activities.

- c. The Corp and/or applicant shall educate and inform personnel involved in the project as to the *Conservation Measures* and *Term and Condition* in this biological opinion.
- d. The Corps and/or applicant, shall ensure its contractors comply with the *Reporting Requirements* below.

Reporting Requirements

In order to monitor whether the amount or extent of incidental take anticipated from implementation of the proposed project is approached or exceeded, the Corps, shall adhere to the following reporting requirements. Should this anticipated amount or extent of incidental take be exceeded, the Corps must reinitiate formal consultation as per 50 CFR 402.16.

1. The Service must be notified within 24 hours of the finding of any injured or dead listed species or any unanticipated damage to its habitat associated with the proposed project. When an injured or dead individual of the listed species is found, the Corps shall follow the steps outlined in the *Salvage and Disposition of Individuals Taken* section below.
2. Sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species shall be reported to the Service and CNDDDB (<https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/BIOS>).
3. The Corps and/or the applicant shall submit a post-construction compliance report to the San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office within 60 calendar days of the date of the completion of construction activities. This report shall detail (i) dates that construction occurred; (ii) pertinent information concerning the success of the proposed project in meeting the *Conservation Measures*; (iii) an explanation of failure to meet such measures, if any; (iv) known project effects on the salt marsh harvest mouse, if any; (v) occurrences of incidental take of this listed species, if any; (vi) documentation of employee environmental education; and (vii) other pertinent information.

Salvage and Disposition of Individuals Taken

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as the Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, and the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the

disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact person is the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at (916) 930-2664.

REINITIATION – CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes formal consultation for the 505 E. Bayshore Road Remedial Sediment and Soil Cleanup Project as provided in 50 CFR §402.16,

1. Reinitiation of consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency, where discretionary Federal involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law and:
 - a. If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;
 - b. If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;
 - c. If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion or written concurrence; or
 - d. If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.
2. An agency shall not be required to reinitiate consultation after the approval of a land management plan prepared pursuant to 43 U.S.C. 1712 or 16 U.S.C. 1604 upon listing of a new species or designation of new critical habitat if the land management plan has been adopted by the agency as of the date of listing or designation, provided that any authorized actions that may affect the newly listed species or designated critical habitat will be addressed through a separate action-specific consultation. This exception to reinitiation of consultation shall not apply to those land management plans prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604 if:
 - a. Fifteen years have passed since the date the agency adopted the land management plan prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604; and
 - b. Five years have passed since the enactment of Public Law 115-141 [March 23, 2018] or the date of the listing of a species or the designation of critical habitat, whichever is later.

Please address any questions or concerns regarding this response to Kim Squires, Section 7 Division Manager, at Kim_Squires@fws.gov. Please refer to Service file number 2024-0111150-S7-001 in any future correspondence regarding this proposed project.

Sincerely,

Donald Ratcliff
Field Supervisor

LITERATURE CITED

- U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service. 2013. Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California. Sacramento Fish and Wildlife Office, Sacramento, California. xviii + 605 pp.
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- _____. 2021. 5-YEAR REVIEW: Salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*). San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office, Sacramento, California. 29 pp.
https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/tess/species_nonpublish/3643.pdf